

Supplementary Material

Mild heat stress induced adaptive immune response in blood mononuclear cells and leukocytes from mesenteric lymph nodes of primiparous lactating Holstein cows

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Table S1. HSP70.1 5'UTR genotyping of Holstein cows

Animal Number	Treatment	895C/-	1128 G/T
12943	HS	CC	GG
96602	HS	-/-	GT
96715	HS	CC	GG
96788	HS	C/-	GT
96573	HS	-/-	TT
96766	HS	-/-	TT
17066	HS	CC	GT
82735	HS	C/-	GT
96869	HS	C/-	GT
96842	HS	C/-	GT
12942	CON	CC	GG
12948	CON	CC	GT
12946	CON	C/-	GT
12940	CON	CC	TT
96516	CON	CC	GG
82704	CON	C/-	GT
96709	CON	CC	GG
96757	CON	CC	GG
82712	CON	CC	GG
82747	CON	-/-	TT
63290	PF	CC	GG
96656	PF	CC	GT
82674	PF	CC	GG
96593	PF	CC	GG
82737	PF	C/-	GT
12945	PF	CC	GG
98550	PF	C/-	GT
98556	PF	C/-	GT
96614	PF	C/-	GT
12944	PF	C/-	TT

Table S2. Primer sequence.

Gene		Primer sequence (5' to 3')	GenBank accession no.	Product size (bp)	Annealing (°C)	PCR efficiency	Ref.
<i>CAT</i>	forward	TCACTCAGGTGCGGACTTTC	NM_001035386	162	60	1.80	(1)
	reverse	GGATGCGGGAGCCATATTCA					
<i>CD14</i>	forward	ACACAACAGAACCCTGCGAG	XM_005209429.4	103	60	1.83	
	reverse	GCAACCATACTGAACGGC					
<i>CCL20</i>	forward	GCAAGCAACTTCGACTGCTG	XM_005202887.4	124	60	1.84	
	reverse	TGGTGTAAGACAACACTGCA					
<i>CCL25</i>	forward	CTCAAGGTGCCTTTGAGGACT	NM_001046569.2	91	60	1.81	
	reverse	TCCTGGCGATGGTAACTCTG					
<i>CCR6</i>	forward	CAACGCCATGTGCAAACCTGA	NM_001194961.1	161	60	1.83	
	reverse	AGATCAGCTTGTGGTGAGCC					
<i>CCR7</i>	forward	AGCTAGCCCTGCTGAGCTATAA	NM_001024930.3	115	60	1.77	
	reverse	TCATCTTGGCAGAGGCACAC					
<i>CCR9</i>	forward	CCACAGAAGCCACAAGCCTA	NM_001098068.1	96	60	1.85	
	reverse	AGTAGTCCGTGAAGTTGCCG					
<i>HSPA1A</i>	forward	AGTCGTACGCCTTCAACATGA	NM_203322.3	79	60	1.74	(2)
	reverse	TTCTTCTTGTCCTCGCT					
<i>IL1B</i>	forward	AACGTCTCCGACGAGTTTC	NM_174093.1	163	60	1.79	(3)
	reverse	GCTCATGCAGAACCACTTC					
<i>IL2</i>	forward	CAAGCTCTACGGGGAACACA	XM_024979646.1	146	60	1.84	
	reverse	TGTAGCGTTAACCTTGGGCA					
<i>IL4</i>	forward	TCCCAGTGCTGGTCTGCTTA	NM_173921.2	149	60	1.75	
	reverse	AAAGACGTCTGCTACAGGCA					
<i>IL6</i>	forward	TCACTCCATTCGCTGTCTCC	NM_173923.2	162	60	1.83	
	reverse	TGTCGACCATGCGCTTAATG					
<i>IL10</i>	forward	CTTAAGGGTTACCTGGGTTGC	NM_174088.1	262	60	1.82	
	reverse	CTCACTCATGGCTTTGTAGACAC					
<i>IL12b</i>	forward	TCATCAAACCAGACCCACC	NM_174356.1	85	60	1.87	
	reverse	TCAGGGTACTCCCAGCTGAC					
<i>IL18</i>	forward	ACCAGGGAAATCAACCTGTCT	NM_174091.2	133	60	1.85	
	reverse	TGCACAGAGATGGTTACGGC					
<i>INFG</i>	forward	TGTGGGCTTTTGGGTTTTTCTG	NM_174086.1	119	60	1.88 (MLN)	
	reverse	AAGAGAGGCCACCCTTAGC				1.90 (PBMC)	
<i>ITGB7</i>	forward	GGATCCCAATCTGTCCCTGC	XM_015470946.2	110	60	1.84	
	reverse	ACGCTGTGAAGTTCAGTTGC					
<i>PPIA</i>	forward	GGATTTATGTGCCAGGGTGGTGA	XM_001252497	120	60	1.79	
	reverse	CAAGATGCCAGGACCTGTATG					
<i>RELA</i>	forward	CAACCCCTTCCAAGTTCCCA	NM_001080242.2	229	60	1.80	
	reverse	CAGGAAGATCTCATCCCCGC					

<i>SOD1</i>	forward	AAGGCCGTGTGCGTGCTGAA	NM_174615.2	246	60	1.85	(1)
	reverse	CAGGTCTCCAACATGCCTCT					
<i>TLR4</i>	forward	ACATTAGTTACCAGTGCATGGAG	NM_174198.6	198	60	1.82	
	reverse	GGCCCTGAAATGTGTCGTCT					
<i>TLR2</i>	forward	GGTTTTAAGGCAGAATCGTTTG	NM_174197	160	60	1.80	
	reverse	AAGGCACTGGGTAAACTGTGT					
<i>TNFA</i>	forward	AGAGGGAAGAGCAGTCCCCAG	NM_173966.3	181	60	1.80 (MLN)	(3)
	reverse	TTCACACCGTTGGCCATGAG				1.86 (PBMC)	
<i>YWHAZ</i>	forward	GAAAGGGATTGTGGACCAG	NM_174814	183	60	1.81	
	reverse	GGCTTCATCAAATGCTGTCT					

Table S3. Normalized protein abundance data of TLR2/4 and ratio p-NF- κ B p65/NF- κ B p65.

Animal Number	Treatment	TLR2	TLR4	p-NF- κ B p65/NF- κ B p65
12943	HS	79.60	57.77	0.77
17066	HS	74.12	312.35	0.64
82735	HS	95.41	153.06	1.23
96573	HS	202.97	71.07	0.64
96602	HS	784.21	133.32	1.35
96715	HS	281.72	177.71	0.61
96766	HS	90.52	384.67	1.00
96788	HS	127.98	85.66	0.47
96842	HS	131.36	120.54	0.71
96869	HS	129.35	256.14	0.77
12940	CON	160.05	168.42	0.58
12942	CON	162.71	188.16	0.87
12946	CON	66.15	171.63	0.37
12948	CON	340.35	150.86	1.32
82704	CON	68.90	109.40	0.59
82712	CON	106.48	191.43	0.62
82747	CON	117.19	242.99	0.44
96516	CON	21.10	207.22	0.90
96709	CON	106.40	161.75	0.69
96757	CON	87.68	68.18	0.42
12944	PF	87.82	588.00	0.62
12945	PF	40.36	40.88	0.35
63290	PF	123.92	109.86	0.64
82674	PF	15.50	127.35	0.58
82737	PF	30.96	114.66	0.50
96593	PF	55.24	180.98	1.18
96614	PF	127.74	346.28	1.03
96656	PF	49.14	338.87	0.66
98550	PF	60.96	118.98	0.41
98556	PF	119.72	197.71	0.84

For the normalization of the protein abundance, the same 7 protein bands of each lane were quantified after Ponceau S staining. The mean intensity was utilized for normalization of the protein data. On each Western blot, a pool sample was added to normalize the different blots to each other.

Figure S1. Exemplarily representation of Western blot for (A) TLR2, (B) TLR4, (C) NF- κ B p65 and (D) p-NF- κ B p65 detection.

Figure S2. Exemplarily representation of Western Blot after Ponceau S staining.

Figure S3. Effects of heat stress, pair-feeding (PF) to their heat-stressed (HS)-counterparts or control (CON) at thermoneutral conditions on plasma (A) cortisol, (B) haptoglobin, (C) tumor necrosis factor α , and (D) interferon γ concentrations normalized to the start of the experimental period (0 h). $n = 10$ cows per treatment. All data are given as LSmean \pm SEM. Different lowercase letters indicate $P < 0.05$ and uppercase letters indicate a trend $0.05 < P < 0.09$.

Figure S4. Effects of heat stress, pair-feeding (PF) to their heat-stressed (HS)-counterparts or control (CON) at thermoneutral conditions on (A) plasma superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme activity and (B) plasma SOD enzyme activity normalized to the start of the challenge at 0 h (Δ SOD enzyme activity). HS cows (red) were kept at AT = 28°C (THI = 76), PF (blue) and control cows (black) were exposed to 16°C (THI = 60) for 7 days. n = 10 cows per treatment. All data are given as LSmean \pm SEM. Different uppercase letters indicate a trend $0.05 < P < 0.09$.

Figure S5. Relative mRNA abundance of genes involved in the TLR2/4-signaling pathway and cytokine expression in leucocytes of mesenteric lymph node after 7 days of heat stress (HS), pair-feeding (PF) to their HS-counterparts or control (CON) at thermoneutral conditions. (A) Heat Shock Protein Family A Member 1A (*HSPA1A*), (B) Interleukin 2 (*IL2*), (C) Interleukin 18 (*IL18*), (D) Interleukin 10 (*IL10*) and (E) Interleukin 12b (*IL12b*). HS cows (red) were heat-stressed (AT = 28°C, THI = 76), PF (blue) and control cows (black) were exposed to 16°C and THI of 60 for 7 days. n = 10 cows per treatment. All data are given as LSmean ± SEM.

References

1. Koch F, Thom U, Albrecht E, Weikard R, Nolte W, Kuhla B, et al. Heat stress directly impairs gut integrity and recruits distinct immune cell populations into the bovine intestine. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 2019.
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3. Gruse J, Kanitz E, Weitzel JM, Tuchscherer A, Stefaniak T, Jawor P, et al. Quercetin Feeding in Newborn Dairy Calves Cannot Compensate Colostrum Deprivation: Study on Metabolic, Antioxidative and Inflammatory Traits. *PloS one*. 2016;11(1):e0146932.